

Stabilities of Some Lanthanide-EDTA-Amino Acid Ternary Complexes

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Formation constants ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) of the mixed ligand complexes of the type LN-EDTA-L (where LN=La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} or Sm^{III}; L = glycine, α -alanine, leucine or valine) have been determined *pH*-metrically in aqueous media at 25° and $\mu=0.2$ (mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄) by using the extension of Irving-Rossotti technique to ternary systems. The stability sequence with respect to metal ions has been found to be La^{III} < Ce^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III}. The $\Delta \log K$ values are negative for all the ternary systems. However, the $\Delta \Delta \log K$ values are significantly positive. A tentative explanation has been offered for this in terms of intra-molecular hydrophobic ligand-ligand interaction. The possibility of existence of isomeric equilibria between the so-called 'closed' and 'open' forms has also been discussed.

MIxed ligand complexes containing amino acids in ternary systems of biochemical importance have been investigated by Sigel *et al.*¹⁻⁵. Presence of an alkyl side chain in amino acids is found to lower the stability of the resulting binary metal-ligand complex; but in ternary systems with such ligands stability enhancement is observed, particularly when the primary ligand is an aromatic ligand, like α, α' -dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline. Hydrophobic interactions are known to occur⁶ between two aliphatic groups, or between aliphatic and aromatic moieties, even the aromatic ring stacking between two aromatic moieties is included in this category.

The present work has been undertaken to study the ternary systems of the type LN-EDTA-L, where, LN(M)=La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} or Sm^{III}; primary ligand (A)=EDTA; and secondary ligand (L)=glycine, α -alanine, leucine or valine.

Experimental

The lanthanide and EDTA solutions were prepared as described earlier⁴. The amino acids were dissolved in double-distilled water by direct weighing. Aqueous solutions of strength 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ were used. The usual sets were prepared for 1:1 binary (ML) and 1:1:1 ternary (MAL) complexes keeping the ionic strength constant at 0.2 (mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄). The sets were titrated against carbonate-free 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaOH at 25° using a Elico LI-120 digital *pH* meter. Reproducible *pH* readings were plotted against ml of alkali (Figs. not shown). The practical proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_n^H$) and the metal-ligand stability constants of 1:1 binary ($\log K_{ML}^M$) and 1:1:1 ternary ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) complexes were

evaluated by using the Irving-Rossotti *pH*-titration technique⁵ and its extension to ternary systems⁶ of the type, $M + A \rightleftharpoons MA$; $MA + L \rightleftharpoons MAL$.

Results and Discussion

The experimental values of $\log K_{ML}^M$, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M)$, and $-\Delta G (= 2.303 RT \log K_{MAL}^{MA})$ are presented in Table 1.

The stability sequence with respect to metal ions (Table 1) has been found to be La^{III} < Ce^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III}, which is the order of increasing occupancy of the 4f-orbitals of these lanthanides accompanied by a gradual decrease in their ionic radii. The stability order with regard to secondary ligands is gly < leu < α -ala < val, which is the order of their basic strength except α -ala.

The $\Delta \log K$ values are negative, which should be primarily due to electrostatic repulsion between (LN-EDTA)⁻ and the incoming secondary ligand L⁻ during the formation of mixed-ligand complexes. $\Delta \log K$ may be expressed as the equilibrium constant for the reaction, $MA + ML = MAL + M$ (1), and its value may be regarded as a measure of the coordination tendency of L towards MA relative to M (charges on the species have been omitted for the sake of simplicity). The statistically expected value of $\Delta \log K$ depends on the geometry of the complex and the denticity of the ligands⁷. In the present case the $-\Delta \log K$ values are relatively smaller for leucine and valine, which indicates a greater stabilisation of the ternary complexes with these ligands, although they possess a fairly large side chain as, CH₃-(α -alanine), (CH₃)₂CH-(valine), and (CH₃)₂CH.CH₂-(leucine).

TABLE 1— $\log K_{ML}^M$, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, $\Delta \log K$ and ΔG (kcal mol⁻¹) Values

Secondary ligand	Property	I = 0.2 (mol dm ⁻³ NaClO ₄)				
		Temp. = 25°				
		Values for metal ions				
		La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}
Glycine (gly)	$\log K_{ML}^M$	5.82	5.98	5.55	5.68	5.84
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.09	4.32	4.68	4.89	4.97
	$-\Delta \log K$	1.28	1.06	0.92	0.79	0.87
	$-\Delta G$	5.86	5.99	6.42	6.78	6.89
α -Alanine (α -ala)	$\log K_{ML}^M$	5.82	6.08	6.86	6.52	6.68
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.93	4.40	4.99	5.17	5.37
	$-\Delta \log K$	1.54	1.68	1.87	1.35	1.31
	$-\Delta G$	5.87	6.04	6.85	7.09	7.88
Leucine (leu)	$\log K_{ML}^M$	5.61	5.84	5.99	6.03	6.18
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.31	4.59	4.72	4.92	5.09
	$-\Delta \log K$	1.80	1.25	1.27	1.09	1.09
	$-\Delta G$	5.97	6.86	6.54	6.82	7.05
Valine (val)	$\log K_{ML}^M$	5.94	6.05	6.28	6.52	6.68
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	5.10	5.83	5.45	5.86	6.05
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.84	0.72	0.83	0.66	0.63
	$-\Delta G$	6.99	7.31	7.48	8.04	8.31

The greater stabilisation of the ternary complexes may be tentatively explained on the basis of a cooperative effect¹ between the primary and secondary ligands in these cases. The possibilities of stereoselectivity, indirect cooperative effects and intramolecular covalent bond formation being ruled out, the existence of intramolecular hydrophobic interactions may be examined by calculating the $\Delta \Delta \log K$ values,

$$\Delta \Delta \log K = \log K_1 - \log K_2$$

The large-sized ligands (l) are leucine and valine, whereas α -alanine may be regarded as the small-sized ligand (s). Glycine has not been chosen for comparison in view of the exceptional stabilities of glycinato chelates^{2,3}. The calculated values of $\Delta \Delta \log K$ are shown in Table 2.

Positive and significant values of $\Delta \Delta \log K$ for the systems [LN-EDTA-(leu/ α -ala)] and [LN-EDTA-(val/ α -ala)] may be regarded as an evidence of hydrophobic interaction responsible for relatively greater stabilisation of the ternary lanthanide complexes with leucine and valine. $\Delta \Delta \log K$ value may be considered as the equilibrium constant for reaction (2).

Positive values of $\Delta \Delta \log K$ indicate that ligand selectivity occurs causing a shift in the above equilibrium towards right.

TABLE 2—POSSIBILITY OF OCCURRENCE OF INTRA-MOLECULAR HYDROPHOBIC LIGAND-LIGAND INTERACTION IN TERNARY LANTHANIDE-EDTA-AMINO ACID COMPLEXES

System	$\Delta \Delta \log K$ for metal ions				
	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}
LN-EDTA-(leu/ α -ala)	+0.24	+0.88	+0.10	+0.26	+0.22
LN-EDTA-(val/ α -ala)	+0.60	+0.91	+0.54	+0.69	+0.68
LN-EDTA-(leu/val)	-0.44	-0.53	-0.44	-0.43	-0.46
LN-EDTA-(leu/ α -ala)*	+0.42	+0.15	+0.36	+0.85	—

* Values obtained by calculating the hydrolysis corrected (C. R. Jejurkar and P. K. Bhattacharya, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 622) values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$. Standard deviations calculated

for the $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values in each case.

The hydrophobic interaction causes a kind of weak linking between the alkyl side chain of the amino acid and the electronic cloud (rather diffused in the present case) over the donors of the primary ligand. All the ternary species donot, however, exist in the linked (closed) form. There exists an isomeric equilibrium in solution between the two isomeric forms 'closed' and 'open' as shown below.

The equilibrium constant, K_i of this equilibrium is given by,

$$K_i = \frac{[\text{EDTA-LN-L}_{cl}]}{[\text{EDTA-LN-L}_{op}]} = \frac{[\text{MAL}_{cl}]}{[\text{MAL}_{op}]} \quad (4)$$

It may be termed 'intramolecular hydrophobic stabilisation constant'. Its numerical value will give the proportion of closed (cl) isomer existing in equilibrium with the open (op) isomer in solution. Equation (1) may be written in the modified form in such a case as,

The experimental value of $\Delta \log K_{exp}$ may be written as,

$$\Delta \log K_{exp} = [MAL_{cl} + MAL_{op}][M]/[MA][ML] \quad (6)$$

In the absence of any hydrophobic interaction the equilibrium is,

and the equilibrium constant, $\Delta \log K_{op}$ is given by,

$$\Delta \log K_{op} = [MAL_{op}][M]/[MA][ML] \quad (8)$$

Combination of equations (4), (6) and (8) and rearrangement of terms give,

$$K_i = \left(\frac{10 \Delta \log K_{exp}}{10 \Delta \log K_{op}} - 1 \right) \quad (9)$$

Regarding the $\Delta \log K$ values in the case of leucine and valine as $\Delta \log K_{exp}$ and that for α -alanine (neglecting any hydrophobic interaction in its case,

TABLE 3 - INTRAMOLECULAR HYDROPHOBIC STABILISATION CONSTANTS (K_i) AND PERCENTAGE OF CLOSED FORMS (% (MAL_{C1})) IN TERNARY SYSTEMS

Ternary complex		Property	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}
Present work	EDTA-LN-leu	K _i	0.73	1.89	0.02	0.82	0.66
		%(MAL _{C1})	42.4	58.0	~2.0	45.2	39.8
	EDTA-LN-leu*	K _i	1.68	0.41	1.29	1.23	—
		%(MAL _{C1})	62.1	29.8	56.4	55.0	—
	EDTA-LN-val	K _i	2.98	7.12	2.47	3.89	3.78
		%(MAL _{C1})	74.2	87.6	71.2	79.5	79.0
Ternary system			K _i		%(MAL _{C1})		
Literature values**	(a) Aromatic-metal-aromatic type :						
		Phen-Cu-tyr		0.58		37	
		Phen-Co-tyr		1.0		50	
		Hist-Cu-phen		1.2		55	
	(b) Aromatic-metal-aliphatic type :						
		Phen-Cu-nval		0.12		11	
		Tyr-Ni-nleu		0.15		18	
		Tyr-Co-nval		0.29		22	
	(c) Aliphatic-metal-aliphatic type :						
		nval-Cu-abu		0.10		~9	
	nval-Ni-abu		0.05		~5		

* Values obtained using hydrolysis corrected values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$.

** Ref. 2.

since the side chain, CH₂, is very small) as an approximation, as $\Delta \log K_{op}$, it is possible to calculate the values of K_i. The calculated values of K_i for the present systems are recorded in Table 3. Some literature values² for various types of systems are also included for comparison.

It may be noted from the data in Table 3 that percentage of the closed isomer in the lanthanide systems is relatively higher as compared to aliphatic-metal-aliphatic type ternary systems involving a 3d-transitional metal ion. Although a larger number of systems of different types should be studied before a firm generalisation may be made, however, looking at the present set of literature values a tentative order in which % (MAL_{C1}) isomers exist in equilibrium with the (MAL_{op}) isomer seems to be Ar-M-Ar > Ar-M-Al > Al-M-Al. Such interactions in ternary complexes are of considerable biochemical importance².

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